

Sorption of Carbofuran (2,3-Dihydro-2,2-dimethylbenzofuranyl-methylcarbamate) by Soil

TAMAL K. JANA and BISWANATH DAS*

Department of Agricultural Chemistry & Soil Science, Faculty of Agriculture, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Mohanpur-741 252

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Sorption of the insecticide Carbofuran by four different soils of West Bengal have been investigated. Adsorption equilibria studies indicated that adsorption of the insecticide by soil was complete within 3 h. The adsorption isotherm yielding S-shaped curve could be described by Freundlich equation. The order of adsorption capacity (K) of the soils for Carbofuran has been evaluated from the values of constant K and $1/n$. Freundlich K values have been correlated with organic matter ($r = 0.951$) and surface area ($r = 0.957$) of the soils. Thermodynamic parameters have been evaluated which indicate the process to be spontaneous but more or less physical in nature.

The adsorption-desorption of pesticides by active soil surface is one of the main processes controlling soil-pesticide interaction¹ because adsorption phenomena can influence the translocation, volatility, persistence and bioactivity of a pesticide². Carbofuran (2,3-dihydro-2,2-dimethylbenzofuranyl-methylcarbamate) is widely used in West Bengal because of the increasing concern over the adverse effects of high persistent chlorinated and some other pesticides on the environment as well as for the control of specific pests which are not being effectively controlled by other insecticides. Accordingly, the present study was undertaken to find out the sorption pattern and mechanisms of adsorption of Carbofuran on some soils of West Bengal.

Results and Discussion

The physicochemical characteristics of the soils are presented in Table 1. The adsorption equilibria for Carbofuran studied on the soils of Bolpur (soil-I) and Barokodali (soil-III) show that the adsorption gradually increased with the passage of shaking time and reached a maximum after 3.0 h. That means that the equilibrium was fully attained within 3 h.

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SOILS

Parameter	Soil-I	Soil-II	Soil-III	Soil-IV
Organic carbon (%)	0.234	0.675	0.990	0.640
Organic matter (%)	0.40	1.16	1.70	1.10
pH (soil : water, 1 : 2.5)	5.0	6.1	5.4	5.9
EC(dSm ⁻¹)	0.34	0.61	0.15	0.16
CEC (Cmol p ⁺ kg ⁻¹)	6.4	14.5	13.9	12.6
Clay content (%)	19.15	31.60	25.35	23.75
Free Fe ₂ O ₃ (%)	1.32	1.70	1.23	0.87
Free Al ₂ O ₃ (%)	0.42	0.73	0.77	0.67
Specific surface area (m ² g ⁻¹)	75	97	112	103

The adsorption isotherms (Fig. 1) yielded S-shaped curves³ which indicate multilayer adsorption and vertical orientation of adsorbed pesticide molecules at the surface with the availability of new sites to the solvent as adsorp-

tion occurs. It also suggests that solvent and solute compete each other for adsorption sites on the soil colloidal surface. The upward nature of the curves indicates that after complete adsorption on adsorbent surface, the adsorbate molecules attract each other and get associated on adsorbent surface⁴.

Adsorption-desorption of Carbofuran on the soils has been described with the empirical Freundlich adsorption equation,

$$\log x/m = \log K + 1/n \log C_e$$

where, x is the amount of (μg) of Carbofuran adsorbed, m the weight (g) of soil, C_e the equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate in solution ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$) and K and $1/n$ are the constants. The constant K has been variously defined as the adsorbent capacity for the adsorbate⁵ and the extent or degree of adsorption⁶, while $1/n$ provides a rough estimate of the intensity of adsorption⁵. The values of K and $1/n$ (Table 2) for Carbofuran on each soil were obtained from $\log x/m$ vs $\log C_e$ plots as the intercept and slope respectively, of each line. All the regression lines possessed a coefficient of determination of at least 0.98, which indicates an excellent fit of the data by the Freundlich equation.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF FREUNDLICH PARAMETERS FOR THE SORPTION OF CARBOFURAN ON SOILS

Soil sample	K	$1/n$
		Adsorption :
Soil-I	0.409	1.185
Soil-II	0.525	1.051
Soil-III	0.742	1.361
Soil-IV	0.607	1.583
		Desorption :
Soil-I	0.693	1.151
Soil-II	0.959	0.913
Soil-III	1.604	1.322
Soil-IV	0.852	1.651

As illustrated by the values of constants K and $1/n$, the order of adsorption capacity of soils for Carbofuran are : Barokodali > Dudherkuthi > Nalhati > Bolpur. The greater

adsorption of Carbofuran on Dudherkuthi soil than that on Nalhathi soil in spite of its high organic matter content, was presumably linked with the low pH and the greater surface area of the former (Table 1). This gets qualitative support from some other observations⁷ also. The intensity of Carbofuran adsorption as indicated by the values of $1/n$ are found to be greater than unity for all the soils and in the order : Dudherkuthi > Barokodali > Bolpur > Nalhathi. The variable slopes of the sorption isotherms obtained for the different pesticides-soil systems studied reveal that pesticide sorption on soil is a complex phenomenon involving different types of adsorption sites.

The desorption K values were consistently higher than those for adsorption (Table 2). This is because of higher amount of Carbofuran retained after desorption than that for adsorption at unit equilibrium concentration. Hysteresis phenomena from the desorption isotherms indicate that different range of forces are involved in the sorption processes of Carbofuran on the soils. The relationship between sorption and soil properties was determined through simple correlation analysis. Four K values so obtained were correlated separately with the eight physicochemical characteristics of the soil. In simple correlation analysis, Freundlich K for Carbofuran was significantly and positively correlated with organic matter ($r = 0.951$) and surface area ($r = 0.957$) of the soils.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS ASSOCIATED WITH SORPTION OF CARBOFURAN ON SOILS

Soil Sample	K_{om}	K_o	ΔG^0 kcal mol ⁻¹
Adsorption :			
Soil-I	102.25	2.84	-0.632
Soil-II	45.25	2.96	-0.657
Soil-III	43.64	3.25	-0.714
Soil-IV	55.18	2.90	-0.645
Average K_{om}	61.58		
ΔG_{om} (kcal)			-2.497
Desorption :			
Soil-I	173.25		
Soil-II	82.26		
Soil-III	94.35		
Soil-IV	77.45		
Average K_{om}	106.82		
ΔG_{om} (kcal)			-2.830

Sorption relationship of Carbofuran was illustrated in a different manner by normalizing the Freundlich K constants to a 1-g, organic matter basis (Table 3). The new constant, K_{om} ($K_{om} = K \times 100/\text{percent organic matter}$) was averaged over the four soils. Assuming that the Carbofuran was adsorbed mainly by organic matter, the change in free energy for adsorption was calculated for the pesticide by using the mean value for K_{om} and the equation given by Osgerby⁸,

$$\Delta G_{om} = -RT \ln K_{om}$$

where, ΔG_{om} is the free energy change (kcal mol⁻¹), R the gas constant (cal K⁻¹ mol⁻¹), and T the temperature (K). The ΔG_{om} was negative (calculated for 303 K), indicating that adsorption of Carbofuran on soil was a spontaneous process (Table 3). However, low values of ΔG_{om} reveal more or less physical nature of the adsorption on the soil organic matter surface.

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherms of carbofuran on soils : (x) Soil-I, (Δ) soil-II, (□) soil-III and (*) soil-IV.

The values of thermodynamic equilibrium constant, K_o (or the thermodynamic distribution coefficient) and standard free energy, ΔG^0 of adsorption for Carbofuran on each soil were calculated by the method of Biggar and Cheung⁹. The values of K_o were obtained by plotting in (C_s/C_e) vs C_s and extrapolating to zero C_s . Here, C_s is μg of solute adsorbed per ml of the solvent in contact with the adsorbent surface and C_e is μg of solute per millilitre of the solvent in the equilibrium solutions. C_s was calculated using the equation,

$$C_s = \frac{(\rho/M)A}{S/N(x/m)}$$

where, ρ is the density of solvent (g cm^{-3}), M the molecular weight of the solvent (g mol^{-1}), A the cross-sectional area of the solvent molecule ($\text{cm}^2/\text{molecule}$), N the Avogadro number, S the surface area of the adsorbent ($\text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$) and x/m the specific adsorption ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$). The cross-sectional area of the solvent molecules was estimated from the equation,

$$A = 1.091 \times 10^{-16} \left[\frac{M \times 10^{24}}{N\rho} \right]^{2/3}$$

Thus, by obtaining K_o , the standard free energy (ΔG^0) for the adsorption was calculated from the equation,

$$\Delta G^0 = -RT \ln K_o$$

The negative values of ΔG^0 (Table 3) in all cases indicated the spontaneous nature of adsorption for Carbofuran on the soils. Low values of ΔG^0 further reveal that adsorption of Carbofuran is more or less physical in nature.

Experimental

Four surface soils (0–20 cm) were collected from different cultivated soil areas of West Bengal with no recent history of pesticide application : lateritic soils of Bolpur (Soil-I) and Nalhathi (Soil-II) in the district of Birbhum, and

Terai alluvial soils of Barokodali (Soil-III) and Dudherkuthi (Soil-IV) in the district of Coochbehar. The soil samples were air-dried, crushed and sieved through a 80-mesh sieve.

A pure sample of Carbofuran (Rallis India Ltd.) was obtained by the recrystallization.

To establish the insecticide adsorption equilibrium in relation to time on the soil system, the insecticide solution (20 ml in 0.02 M CaCl₂) was added to air-dried soil sample (2 g) in 50-ml glass centrifuge tube and shaken for 0.25–36 h. The tubes were centrifuged and suitable aliquots were then taken from the collected centrifugate for spectrophotometric analysis of the insecticide¹⁰.

After centrifugation and removal of aliquots for spectrophotometric analysis, the remaining supernatant was carefully decanted. A 0.02 M CaCl₂ solution (20 ml) was added back to the tubes and the sample was shaken for 3 h. The tubes were centrifuged and supernatant solution from each tube was removed for the spectrophotometric determination of the insecticide. Desorption ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$ soil) was determined by the difference, taken into account the solution remaining in the soil after the supernatant was poured off.

Carbofuran was estimated following the reported procedure¹¹ with slight modifications. To the decanted supernatant aliquot (5 ml) were added 0.3% sodium nitrite (2.5

ml) and 0.2% sulfanilic acid (2.5 ml) in 1 N HCl and the mixture was allowed to stand for 15 min. Then 4 N NaOH (5 ml) was added and the solution was boiled on a water-bath for 15 min after which the volume was made up to 25 ml with distilled water. Absorbance of the orange colour of the solution was measured by a spectrophotometer (Bausch & Lomb Spectronic-20) at 490 nm after 30 min.

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